

BASIC SULPHATES OF BIVALENT METALS (Cd, Cu, Zn). PART III. ZINC

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The basic sulphates $\text{ZnSO}_4 \cdot 3\text{Zn}(\text{OH})_2$ and $\text{ZnSO}_4 \cdot \text{Zn}(\text{OH})_2$ have been shown to exist by thermometric method.

Various basic sulphates have been described in the literature by different authors. But according to Lubkowskaia (*J. Russ. Phys. Chem. Soc.*, 1917, 39, 989) the basic sulphate $\text{ZnSO}_4 \cdot 3\text{ZnO} \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ exists only as a definite compound. The potentiometric titrations (Nikurashiu, *J. Gen. Chem. U.S.S.R.*, 1938, 8, 1454) of zinc sulphate solutions with alkali show the existence of the compound $\text{ZnSO}_4 \cdot 3\text{Zn}(\text{OH})_2$ or $\text{ZnSO}_4 \cdot 3\text{ZnO}$. Hagusawa (*Bull. Inst. Phys. Chem. Res.*, Tokyo, 1939, 18, 368) has stated that the potentiometric titrations of zinc sulphate solution with alkali show the existence of the compound $\text{ZnSO}_4 \cdot 3\text{Zn}(\text{OH})_2$ when the concentration of zinc sulphate is 0.0074 g. mol. per litre and the compound $\text{Zn}(\text{OH})_2$ when zinc sulphate concentration is 0.0004955 g. mol. per litre. No indication of the basic salt $\text{ZnSO}_4 \cdot \text{ZnO}$ has been observed by the potentiometric method although literatures on the basic sulphate of zinc mention a compound of the formula $(\text{ZnOH})_2\text{SO}_4$ (Athanasesco, *Compt. rend.*, 1886, 103, 271) which is equivalent to $\text{ZnSO}_4 \cdot \text{Zn}(\text{OH})_2$. Moreover, considering the similarity of Zn with Cd and Cu, it is expected that zinc will also give a basic sulphate of the formula $\text{ZnSO}_4 \cdot \text{Zn}(\text{OH})_2$ particularly in concentrated solutions. So, here zinc sulphate solution has been titrated with caustic soda solution to see whether the indications of the two basic sulphates, $\text{ZnSO}_4 \cdot 3\text{ZnO}$ and $\text{ZnSO}_4 \cdot \text{ZnO}$, as in the case of Cd and Cu, are obtained.

EXPERIMENTAL

The thermometric arrangement is the same as that has been described in Part I of the series (*This Journal*, 1946, 23, 147). The reagents used were of 'Analar' quality. Standard solutions of zinc sulphate were prepared by direct weighing and standard solutions of caustic soda were prepared by standardising with potassium bi-iodate using Wesslow as an indicator

TABLE I

NaOH soln. = 1.0611*M*. ZnSO₄ soln. = 0.26528*M*, taken = 40 c.c. (Fig. 1).

NaOH added.	Temp.	Rise in temp.	Total rise (in temp.)
0 c.c.	3.130°	0.000°	0.000°
1	3.030	0.100	0.100
2	2.920	0.110	0.210
3	2.810	0.110	0.320
4	2.700	0.110	0.430
5	2.500	0.100	0.530
6	2.500	0.100	0.630
7	2.410	0.090	0.720
8	2.320	0.090	0.810
9	2.220	0.100	0.910
10	2.170	0.050	0.960
11	2.120	0.050	1.010
12	2.080	0.040	1.050
13	2.055	0.025	1.075
14	2.030	0.025	1.100
15	2.010	0.020	1.120
16	2.000	0.010	1.130
18	1.980	0.020	1.150
20	1.970	0.010	1.160
22	1.950	0.020	1.180
24	1.940	0.010	1.190
26	1.920	0.020	1.210
28	1.910	0.010	1.220

TABLE II

NaOH soln. = 2.0082*M*. ZnSO₄ soln. = 0.20082*M*, taken = 40 c.c. (Fig. 2).

NaOH added.	Temp.	Rise in temp.	Total rise (in temp.)
0.0 c.c.	4.605°	0.000°	0.000°
1.0	4.480	0.125	0.125
2.0	4.330	0.150	0.275
3.0	4.210	0.120	0.395
4.0	4.085	0.125	0.520
5.0	3.970	0.115	0.635
5.5	3.940	0.030	0.665
6.0	3.910	0.030	0.695
7.0	3.860	0.050	0.745
7.5	3.830	0.030	0.775
8.0	3.800	0.030	0.805
8.5	3.790	0.010	0.815
9.0	3.770	0.020	0.835
10.0	3.745	0.025	0.860
11.0	3.745	0.000	0.860
12.0	3.745	0.000	0.860
13.0	3.745	0.000	0.860
14.0	3.745	0.000	0.860
15.0	3.745	0.000	0.860

TABLE III

NaOH soln. = 1.0611*M*. ZnSO₄ soln. = 0.13260*M*, taken = 40 c.c. (Fig. 3).

NaOH added.	Temp.	Rise in temp.	Total rise (in temp.)
0 c.c.	3.370*	0.000*	0.000*
1	3.320	0.050	0.050
2	3.250	0.070	0.120
3	3.170	0.080	0.200
4	3.080	0.080	0.280
5	3.010	0.080	0.360
5.5	2.960	0.050	0.410
6.0	2.930	0.030	0.440
6.5	2.890	0.040	0.480
7.0	2.850	0.040	0.520
8.0	2.790	0.060	0.580
8.5	2.770	0.020	0.600
9.0	2.745	0.025	0.625
9.5	2.715	0.030	0.655
10.0	2.700	0.015	0.670
11.0	2.700	0.000	0.670
12.0	2.700	0.000	0.670
13.0	2.700	0.000	0.670
14.0	2.700	0.000	0.670
15.0	2.700	0.000	0.670

TABLE IV

NaOH soln. = 0.50205*M*. ZnSO₄ soln. = 0.050205*M*, taken = 40 c.c. (Fig. 4).

NaOH added.	Temp.	Rise in temp.	Total rise (in temp.)
0 c.c.	4.695*	0.000*	0.000*
1	4.655	0.040	0.040
2	4.610	0.045	0.085
3	4.565	0.045	0.130
4	4.520	0.045	0.175
5	4.480	0.040	0.215
6	4.440	0.040	0.255
7	4.425	0.015	0.270
8	4.410	0.015	0.285
9	4.400	0.010	0.295
10	4.390	0.010	0.305
11	4.380	0.010	0.315
12	4.370	0.010	0.325
13	4.360	0.010	0.335
14	4.350	0.010	0.345

TABLE V

ZnSO₄ soln. = 0.5*M*. NaOH soln. = 0.25*M*, taken = 40 c.c. (Fig. 5).

ZnSO ₄ added.	Temp.	Rise in temp.	Total rise (in temp.)
0 c.c.	5.550*	0.000*	0.000*
1	5.550	0.050	0.050
2	5.450	0.050	0.100
3	5.370	0.080	0.180
4	5.320	0.050	0.230
5	5.260	0.060	0.290
6	5.230	0.030	0.320
7	5.195	0.035	0.355
8	5.155	0.040	0.395
9	5.130	0.025	0.420
10	5.100	0.030	0.450
11	5.000	0.100	0.550
12	4.920	0.080	0.630
13	4.810	0.110	0.740
14	4.770	0.040	0.780
15	4.730	0.040	0.820
16	4.620	0.040	0.860
18	4.630	0.060	0.920
20	4.560	0.070	0.990

DISCUSSION

All the curves show that the basic sulphate $ZnSO_4 \cdot 3Zn(OH)_2$ is formed when caustic soda solution is added to zinc sulphate solution of concentrations $0.050205M$ to $0.26528M$.

FIG. 1.

FIG. 2.

FIG. 3.

The basic sulphate $\text{ZnSO}_4 \cdot \text{Zn}(\text{OH})_2$ is, however, first formed at concentrations $0.20082M$ and $0.26528M$, which reacts with further quantity of alkali to give the compound $\text{ZnSO}_4 \cdot 3\text{Zn}(\text{OH})_2$. Again $\text{ZnSO}_4 \cdot 3\text{Zn}(\text{OH})_2$ reacts with more alkali and passes to $\text{Zn}(\text{OH})_2$.

FIG. 4.

FIG. 5.

But this process is a very slow one, as is often the case with a liquid-solid reacting system. This is also evident from the curves since the break corresponding to $\text{Zn}(\text{OH})_2$ is not observed in all the curves. The reverse titration curve *i.e.*, addition of zinc sulphate solution to alkali shows breaks corresponding to the zincate $\text{Na}_2[\text{Zn}(\text{OH})_4]$, hydroxide $\text{Zn}(\text{OH})_2$ and the basic sulphate $\text{ZnSO}_4 \cdot 3\text{Zn}(\text{OH})_2$. Thus the basic sulphate $\text{ZnSO}_4 \cdot 3\text{Zn}(\text{OH})_2$ is very stable and can be obtained either by adding alkali to zinc sulphate solution or *vice versa* as in the case of Cd. The indication of the existence of the zincate $\text{Na}_2[\text{Zn}(\text{OH})_4]$ is in conformity with the result obtained by Dutoit and Grobet (*J. chim. phys.*, 1921, 19, 324) in the zinc-nitrate-caustic soda system.

Thus it can be concluded that Zn like Cd and Cu gives the same type of basic sulphates and shows complete similarity with Cd and Cu at least with respect to basic salt formation which may be said as the characteristic of this group (Cd, Cu and Zn) of bivalent metals.

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